

PEST DETECTION IN CROPS USING DEEP LEARNING ALGORITHM

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Abstract

Research in the agriculture industry has great potential to reduce food shortages and supply nutritious food. Farmers face a difficult in identifying pests in crops, as pest attacks cause significant crop damage and quality degradation. The disadvantage of traditional pest identification is that it requires skilled taxonomists to correctly identify the pest based on its physical characteristics. In recent years, the relevance of using vision-based technologies for pest monitoring in the agriculture industry has greatly expanded. However, there are currently no automated techniques which can accurately identify plant pests. In this work deep learning based pest detection has been experimented and tried for deployment in real farming field. A segmentation method based on CNN and Deep Learning has been created to do pest identification. The experiment has demonstrated that CNN-based approaches significantly performed good.

Keywords: pest detection, 18 classes of pests, CNN algorithm.

Introduction

Agriculture is regarded as the foundation of the economy, plays a role in the development of the nation's economy and establishes the standard level of living. One of a country's main economic sectors is agriculture and food processing industry. One of the major issues in the agricultural sector that leads to a decline in crop quality is pest attack. Crops are severely damaged by pests, pathogens, and weeds, which leads to a poor market for the finished goods. So this will be must take care of pest attacks on crops that hinder the growth of field crops. In order to assure crop quality and safety in agriculture, it is therefore vital to monitor and evaluate the losses caused by insects.

Recent advancements in the agricultural sector have included the use of machine learning techniques to identify and categorize insects. Eighteen different types of bug photos were classified using deep learning-based algorithms. To enhance the recognition performance for eighteen kinds of crop insects, deep residual learning for pest detection in

complicated backgrounds was developed. Deep residual learning for pest detection in difficult backdrops was created to improve the performance of recognition for 18 different types of crop insects.

For the automatic categorization of field crop pests, a number of unsupervised feature learning techniques and multi-level classification frameworks were developed. According to more recent studies, image processing may be used efficiently for the identification of insects since it is quick to detect and can easily discriminate insects of similar color and shape. Combining region-based and contour-based segmentation, it is used to detect individual moths and touching insects. The best performance in pest classification and detection has recently been attained using powerful deep learning models. These studies involved classifying several types of insect photos using various models that were trained using attributes derived from the insects. In the natural environment, classifying and identifying insects with the same feature types and in different situations is quite challenging.

The applications involving image classification, the deep learning model with low classifier performs poorly, hence performance improvement is required. Insect pest detection algorithms and deep learning based CNN algorithm are used in this study to classify and identify insects as pests easily in field crops.

This project helps to develop a model using CNN algorithm to detect the pests using the dataset which have 18 classes of pest images. Detecting the pest in crops using CNN algorithm is more faster than traditional pest identification method. This method is very helpful for farmers to identify the pest easily in crops and kill them using some pesticides. These processes will help farmers to improve their cultivation and it will helpful for framers to yield healthy fruits, vegetables and grains and so on.

Methodology

There are several processes that must be taken in order to classify insects. , To increase the size of the training dataset, image augmentation is used on photos from the insect dataset. The classification of the insect classes is then performed using CNN deep learning techniques and shape

features that were retrieved from the insect photos. Extraction of shape features. Shape attributes are crucial characteristics that are used in computer vision and automatic object recognition systems which were unaffected by scaling, rotation, and translation. Based on the finite shape features that are derived from the bug photos, insects are classified. The RGB insect photos were changed to grayscale images for additional feature extraction. The classifier models are then applied with the nine shape features, which are area, perimeter, main axis length, minor axis length, eccentricity, circularity, solidity, form factor, and compactness

Framework for proposed work

The image preprocessing process contains three steps as follows:

- a) RGB to grey conversion: In an image, each pixel is represented by the RGB color model, which consists of the colors RED, GREEN, and BLUE. The drawback of RGB models is that they take quite a lot of storage space. Due to the fact that HSV is a suitable color descriptor, RGB is first transformed into HSV space. The following stage entails masking and background removal using a pre-calculated threshold level. The region of interest is created by applying image segmentation using 32x32 patch size images in the following phase (ROI). These segments are also utilized for the color cooccurrence matrix texture analysis. Then, the textural parameters are contrasted with those of a typical leaf.
- b) Resizing the acquired image: A variety of resizing techniques are used. Interpolation using the nearest neighborhood
- c) Image filtering: Filtering is used to enhance images by removing distracting elements from them.
- d) Feature extraction: The most crucial step is feature extraction. So the required features are extracted using preprocessing technique.

Insect Classification with CNN Model

The given dataset bug photos were used to train the CNN model. The CNN model is computationally effective since automatic feature learning and weight sharing are used, and it belongs to the class of deep, feed-forward neural networks used to assess visual imagery of insect images. As shown in Fig.3.2, the CNN model for classifying insect pictures consists of five convolutional layers, three max-pooling layers, a flatten layer, a fully connected layer, and a SoftMax output layer. The insect image is scaled down to a size of 64 X 64. The computational operations per layer and memory needs can be decreased by using the CNN model, which can process each insect image rather quickly. Both the convolution layer and the maxpooling layer employ filter sizes of 3 * 3 and 2 * 2, respectively. The final classification of insects is accomplished by learning high-level information using a fully linked layer. The loaded bug image is scaled to 227 *227. The color image is read by OpenCV. This is a sensible and effective choice to utilize as a classifier for big volume data, such as pest detection. Images are captured from a variety of angles, including top, side, and front perspectives. Additionally, the photos are made noise-free utilizing image processing. The object is then recognized using some feature extraction and deep learning algorithms.

CNN Architecture

System Design

Step 1: Collection of images data from the Kaggle (Benchmark data repository)

Step 2: The next step is to preprocess the data by Image Augmentation.

Step 3: Training the model using CNN algorithm.

Step 4: Predicting the Classification of insects for the given dataset.

Step 5: Test the accuracy of the result.

Step 6: Visualizing the models result for the given dataset.

Experimental Setup

a) Data Collection

The pest image data are collected from the dataset. The images of the dataset are collected from kaggle(benchmark data repository). This dataset contains 3246 images belongs to 18 classes of images. The Class names are ants, aphids, armyworm, beetle, bollworm, Grasshopper, mites, Mosquito, Sawfly, Stem borer, Aulacophora, Bactroera cucurbitae, Caterpillar, Dark evening, Longitarsus, Pentatomomorpha, Planococcus lilacinus, Scirpophaga, Weevil.

b) Data Preprocessing

The fundamental step in image preprocessing is Image Augmentation. Image augmentation is applied in the given dataset. The insect photos were resized to 227* 227 pixels in size. Techniques for enhancing image data, such as rotation, flipping, and cropping operators, are used to expand the training set in order to improve accuracy and get rid of overtraining issues by using eight different operators. The insect photos from the provided dataset are transformed into various images in the enhanced dataset.

c) Model Training

Following Data Pre-processing, deep learning methods are used to train the model and perform Classification. Training and testing portions of the data are separated. Most currently used 10-fold cross-validation, which divides the dataset into 10 equal sections, 9 of which are used to train the algorithm and the remaining set to test its performance. The algorithm used here is to CNN to train the model. CNN is the most popular deep learning algorithm for image recognition and classification. The object is then recognised using some feature extraction and deep learning algorithms. Edge and leaf colour have been chosen as the main features for pest detection. Pixel-to-pixel alignment, the key element of a deep learning-based detection technique is included in CNN. For object identification methods like deep learning (CNN) picture classification approaches, we have used a vision-based system. Many common leaf-based diseases and pests have been found and are now being trained for classification.

Conclusion

Farmers are facing a difficulty in identifying the pest in crops by traditional methods. Hence in this paper, deep learning and insect pest identification system was used to classify and detect various insect using given dataset. To increase the accuracy, all of the insect photos were rescaled, pre-processed, and enhanced. In the real-time field, it can be difficult to classify insects with greater precision because the presence of shadows, leaves, mud, branches, flower buds, etc. in the agricultural field crops. Hence CNN algorithm is used to recognize the image of the pest and classify it effectively. It leads to rapid insect recognition by cutting down on computing time. With minimal computation time, an insect pest detection technique was used to identify insects from the provided datasets

References

1. Johnny L. Miranda, Bobby D. Gerardo, and Bartolome T. Tanguilig III, 'Pest Detection and Extraction Using Image Processing Techniques', International Journal of Computer and Communication Engineering, Vol. 3, No. 3, May 2014
2. Navin V. Dumare 1, Prof. S. S. Mungona 2, 'Identification of Cotton Leaf Diseases Using Raspberry Pi: A Review', International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 6, Issue 3, March 2017.
3. Sreelakshmi M, Padmanayana, 'Early Detection and Classification of Pests Using Image Processing', International Journal of Innovative Research in Electrical, Electronics, Instrumentation and Control Engineering, Vol. 3, Special Issue 1, April 2015
4. Erick SALDANA et. al., '~ 'Review: computer vision applied to the inspection and quality control of fruits and vegetables', Brazilian Journal of Food Technology, Campinas, v. 16, n. 4, p. 254-272, out. /dez. 2013
5. Muhammad Hafeez Javed M Humair Noor Babar Yaqoob Khan, 'Kmeans Based Automatic Pests Detection and Classification for Pesticides Spraying', (IJACSA) International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications. 8 No. 11, 2017
6. G, 'Pest Control in Agricultural Plantations Using Image Processing', OSR Journal of Electronics and Communication Engineering (IOSR-JECE), Volume 6, PP 68-74, Issue 4(May. - Jun. 2013)
7. Paul Boissard, Vincent Martin, Sabine Moisan, 'A Cognitive Vision Approach to Early Pest Detection in Greenhouse Crops', HAL, Preprint submitted to Elsevier 6 November 2007
8. I.M.A. Ebrahimi, M.H. Khoshtaghaza, S. Minaei, B. Jamshidi, " Vision-based pest detection based on SVM classification method", Computers and Electronics in Agriculture, 137, pp 52± 58,201
9. Muhammad Hafeez Javed, M Humair Noor, Babar Yaqoob Khan, " Kmeans Based Automatic Pests Detection and Classification for Pesticides Spraying", (IJACSA) International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications, Vol. 8 No. 11, 2017